

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING DETERMINERS IN ESL CLASSES

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Annotation. In this article it is stated that the signification of determiners of the English grammar in utilizing EFL classes. The research goes on its specularity and importance. Differences and similar sides are compared adequately.

Key words: determiners, articles, demonstrative pronouns, possessives, numerals, cardinals, ordinals, distributives, quantifiers, predeterminers

Аннотация. В этой статье утверждается что значение определителей английской грамматики при использовании классов EFL. Исследования продолжаются на его зеркальности и значимости.

Ключевые слова: определители, притяжательные, порядковые, числительные, кванторы, артикли, преопределители и дистрибутивы.

Annotation. Ushbu maqolada EFL sinflarida foydalanishda ingliz tili grammatikasidagi aniqlovchilarning muhimligi haqida soʻz boradi. Bu tadqiqotda uning oʻziga xosligi va ahamiyati haqida soʻz yuritiladi. Farqlar va oʻxshash tomonlar yetarli darajada taqqoslanadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: aniqlovchi, egalik, son, tartib son, miqdor son, artikl, old aniqlovchi va taqsimlovchi soʻzlar.

Determiners make clear nouns with context in English language. They modifies or describes a noun by using clarifying what it refers to. Determiners do this with the aid of indicating traits such as possession, relative position, and quantity. In a noun phrase, determiners come before nouns. Explore the definition and predominant makes use of determiners and examine about kinds of determiners, along with articles, possessives, demonstratives and quantifiers.

Most native English audio system could not discover a determiner even if it was staring them proper in face. The funny element is that most English audio system use determiners each day in speech and writing. In English, determiners are essential to acceptable sentence shape and comprehension. Determiners are essential because they work to make clear nouns and make a sentence as specific and centered as possible. Many parts of speech, such as articles, demonstratives, quantifiers, and possessives, can be as a determiner. In this lesson, we will go over the definition of the determiner, discuss the kinds of them and discover the uses of determiners.

Determiners are phrases that come till now than a noun and serve to alter the noun. They alter nouns via potential of capacity of ability of attainable of viable of the way of imparting context and specificity to the noun. Let's take a show off up to be at the following sentence and locate out the modifier: This rabbit is very fat. The phrase *'this'* is the determiner. The determiner strikes to specify exactly which rabbit the speaker is referring to in order to make clear and contextualize the information. Many splendid factors of speech can attribute as determiners. Like referred to previously, articles, demonstratives, quantifiers and possessives are the most day-to-day sorts of phrases that can be determiners.

Types of determiners.

Let's take a few moments to look at some unique types of determiners

- I. **Articles.** Articles are usually classified as their personal phase of speech, but they are additionally viewed a kind of determiner. The major articles are 'the', 'a', and 'an'. "The" is a precise article, which talent it refers to a precise person, place, or thing. Using the phrase 'the' as a determiner will extend the exactness of the problem in a sentence. The particular article 'the' is used to refer to a specific noun.

For example:

The moon looks nice tonight.

Can I get the book on the table?

The indefinite articles 'a' and 'an' are used to refer to regular or specific version of a noun. Which indefinite article you use relies upon on the pronunciation of the words that follows. 'A' is used until now than phrases that begin with a consonant sound (e.g: a bird). 'An' used before words that start with a vowel sound (an apricot).

For example:

John consumed an apricot.

Do you like a doll?

Indefinite articles can in addition be used to refer to some difficulty for the first time. Once a noun has been introduced, the magnificent article then be used, as it refers to a before mentioned noun. For instance: *I bought a book. The book is very interesting.*

II. Demonstratives. Learning how to understand and use demonstrative pronouns is very important, for various reasons:

- We hear demonstrative pronouns all the time in day by day conversations, films and TV shows, books and songs. So getting to know them ability you will be capable to apprehend greater of your favourite English media.

- Demonstrative pronouns make speaking English easier. By the usage of phrases like this instead of repeating the title of a noun, we sound extra natural.

- Knowing demonstrative pronouns is fundamental to getting excessive rankings on English proficiency test.

You may additionally already comprehend that is a phrase of sentence functioning as a noun. Let's use this this sentence as an example: ***This little girl*** is very clever.

'**This little girl**' is a noun phrase that is the concern of the total sentence. We can replace this little girl with the phrase '*she*' to get the sentence:

She is very clever.

In this sentence the word *she* is a pronoun.

Let's take a look at a few more examples with pronouns:

-Durdona and I go shopping every Sunday. → ***We*** go shopping every Sunday.

III. Possessive adjectives. Possessive adjectives are used to exhibit possession or ownership of something. While we use them when we refer to people, it is extra the experience of relationship than ownership. The possessive adjective desires to agree with the possessor and not with the component that is possessed.

Examples:

My father is a businessman.

Your bicycle is new.

Their house is expensive.

Like all adjectives in English, they are continually positioned directly in front of the noun they refer to.

We do not include an 's' to the adjective when the noun is plural like in many other languages:

Our home is expensive (correct)

Ours home is expensive (incorrect)

However, the verb that is used wishes be in agreement with the noun – if the noun is singular then the verb is plural:

My pencil is red (singular)

My pencils are red (plural)

Unlike nouns and verbs, the special classes of adjectives are often much less defined. For example, many style guides or sources of grammar recommendation think about possessive adjectives to truly be a category of words regarded as determiners, in which case they can also be referred to as possessive determiners or even just possessives. Unlike many other adjectives, possessive adjectives can act in a similarity to pronouns in that they can substitute possessive nouns. For example, the sentences *I like Susan's hat* and *I like her hat* have the same meaning. Additionally, possessive adjectives cannot be become into superlative or comparative adjectives. Something can be *slower* than something else however something cannot be 'our-er' or 'my-er' than something else.

While this characteristics may additionally help classifying possessive adjectives as an extraordinary discern of speech, we think about phrases like *my*, *your*, and *our* to be adjectives instead than determiners. Not every style guide will take this approach, however, so do not be surprised if you see words like these categorised differently.

- IV. Numerals.** Both cardinal (one, two, three, etc.) and ordinal numbers (first, second, third forth, etc.) can be used as determiners. Cardinal numbers are used to point out the volume of humans and things. They normally follow different determiners in a sentence (e.g. *your two chance*):

Your friend has two sisters.

Ordinal numbers are used to specify the order of nouns in a series. They comply with different determiners in a sentence (e.g. *my fifth birthday*):

You think the first woman with sunglasses is not a thief.

- V. Distributives.** Distributives are used to talk about the components of a team in relation to the complete group. They can be pronouns or determiners. Determiners are phrases that come before nouns to make clear what the noun is referring to. While the same phrase is from time to time used for both, the usage guidelines and sentence structure exchange depending on whether or not they are used as a pronoun or determiner. Distibutive determiners regulate nouns, including compound nouns and applicable nouns. However, there are some one of a kind some special rules for when you can them with singular nouns, plural nouns, which we provide an explanation for below. Distributive determiners (also distributive adjectives) used to refer to a crew or to person to human beings or object inside a group. The distributive determiners are **all, each, both, every, either, half and neither none**:

Both of them are my relatives.

Every year I go abroad with my family.

- VI. Quantifiers.** Quantifiers (also known as indefinite adjectives) point out the quantity of a noun. They **include all, any, few, less, little, many, much, several, no, and some**. They additionally encompass the cardinal numbers (**one, two, three, etc**).

There are several customers in shop.

Some teachers work from 8:00 to 17:00.

- VII. Pre-determiners.** In English grammar, pre-determiners are phrases that are used before than a determiner but are nonetheless phase of noun group. Pre-determiners are regularly quantative words, that may additionally be placed before an article or different determiners. For example 'all' in 'all the cookies' or 'both' in 'both his legs'.

Among the all distributives only two of them are used before determiners. 'All' is used with countable and uncountable nouns, however 'both' is used only with countable nouns. Check out the examples:

All my clothes are new.

All those flowers are yours.

Both her teachers are clever.

‘Both’ and ‘all’ are not used with indefinite article ‘a’ or ‘an’.

So I have arrived at a decision that the determiners in using EFL classes make students’ knowledge about English grammar improved and importance of it, in learning is really perceptible. Apart from this, learners can be easily communicate with each other and they may explain their opinion with determiners during the conversation.

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